

Improving the reliability of cohesion policy databases

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Acronyms

Apl Apulia

AsV Aosta Valley

CF Cohesion Fund

Clb Calabria

Cmp Campania

DG REGIO Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy

EAFRD European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development

EC European Commission

EmR Emilia-Romagna

ERDF European Regional Development Fund

ESF European Social Fund

ESIF European Structural and Investment Funds

EU European Union

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25 **FVG** Friuli Venezia Giulia
26 **IT** Italy
27 **Laz** Lazio
28 **Lgr** Liguria
29 **Lmb** Lombardy
30 **Mls** Molise
31 **MS** Member State
32 **NMAs** National Managing Authorities
33 **NUTS** Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
34 **OPs** Operational Programmes
35 **QoI** Quantity of Interest
36 **Scl** Sicily
37 **Srd** Sardinia
38 **Tsc** Tuscany
39 **TST** Trentino-South Tyrol

40 **Abstract**

41 In this contribution, we present an innovative data-driven model to reconstruct a reliable temporal pattern for
42 time-lagged statistical monetary figures. Our research cuts across several domains regarding the production of
43 robust economic inferences and the bridging of top-down aggregated information from central databases with
44 disaggregated information obtained from local sources or national statistical offices.
45 Our test bed case study is the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). The application we discuss deals
46 with the reported time lag between the local expenditures of ERDF by beneficiaries in Italian regions and the
47 corresponding payments reported in the European Commission database. Our model reconstructs the timing
48 of these local expenditures by back-dating the observed European Commission reimbursements. The inferred
49 estimates are then validated against the expenditures reported from the Italian National Managing Authorities
50 (NMAs) in terms of cumulative monetary difference. The lower cumulative yearly distance of our modelled
51 expenditures compared to the official European Commission payments confirms the robustness of our model.
52 Using sensitivity analysis, we also analyse the relative importance of the modelling parameters on the cumulative
53 distance between the modelled and reported expenditures. The parameters with the greatest influence on the
54 uncertainty of this distance are the following: first, how the non-clearly regionalised expenditures are attributed

55 to individual regions; and second, the number of backward years that the residuals of the yearly payments are
56 spread onto. In general, the distance between the modelled and reported expenditures can be further reduced
57 by fixing these parameters. However, the gain is only marginal for some regions.

58 The present study paves the way for modelling exercises that are aimed at more reliable estimates of the
59 expenditures on the ground by the ultimate beneficiaries of European funds. Additionally, the output databases
60 can contribute to enhancing the reliability of econometric studies on the effectiveness of European Union (EU)
61 funds.

62 **Keywords**

63 Modelling; sensitivity analysis; econometrics; expenditures timing; uncertainty analysis.

64 **Introduction**

65 In this contribution we propose a data-driven model to estimate the actual economic time series from those
66 reported in official centralised databases and benchmark them against bottom-up evidence coming from local
67 statistical offices. The test bed case study is the ERDF, which aims to strengthen economic, social, and ter-
68 ritorial cohesion in the EU by correcting interregional imbalances. ERDF is part of the European Structural
69 and Investment Funds (ESIF), which represent roughly two-thirds of the whole European budget, amounting
70 to more than 1 trillion euros for the period 2014-2020 (approximately 1% of the EU-28 gross national income).
71 For the same peoriod, the ERDF allocated more than 220 billion euros in investments to diverse areas.

72 Additionally, a new temporary instrument, the NextGenerationEU, amounting to 750 billion euros has been
73 introduced for the period 2021-2027 to ease the recovery of EU countries from the COVID-19 pandemic. The
74 extraordinary circumstances that have arisen due to this challenge further emphasise the importance of un-
75 derstanding the spending pattern of public resources [1], particularly so as to inform the public about the
76 allocations of EU tax-payers' money and their benefits.

77 Every Member State (MS) in the EU is obliged to record and account for the expenses incurred, but the com-
78 plete records are neither (always) publicly available nor directly comparable across individual MSs. For this
79 reason, a spatially and temporally homogeneous expenditure database at the European level will always be
80 lacking. This is precisely why resorting to modelling these expenditures can help to alleviate the issue.

81 The European Commission (EC)-managed database suffers from an inevitable time lag because EC payments
82 are reimbursed only after the incurred expenses have been invoiced. Precisely, the final beneficiaries invest on
83 the ground and produce invoices to the NMAs, which, in turn, certify the share of eligible expenditures and
84 produce an invoice to the EC. Even if this process runs smoothly (i.e., the relevant documents are promptly pro-
85 cessed at each stage, no accounting mistakes are made, payments are not suspended following audit inspections,
86 and so on), a substantial time lag may occur from the incurred expenditure on the ground to the moment when
87 the EC payment to the NMAs is actually recorded. Therefore, it is very challenging to produce econometric

88 inferences regarding the benefits of EU cohesion policy funding on the ground.
89 The model we discuss in this contribution estimates the expenditures incurred by European regions from their
90 observed EC reimbursement pattern. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first time this approach is at-
91 tempted. Our modelled expenditures are validated against the expenditures reported by the Italian authorities,
92 which have recently become available.
93 Econometricians can make use of the [output database of modelled expenditures](#) to generate more robust infer-
94 ences regarding the benefits of EU cohesion policy in a number of fields, including convergence analysis [2–6]
95 and in terms of the effects on GDP [7, 8], employment [7], or local administrative and governance capacity
96 [9–11] among many others.
97 The next section presents the data and methods used for the present study. In addition, we demonstrate how a
98 Wasserstein measure [12], which gives the distance between two curves, is a convenient proxy to drive inferences
99 on the observed reimbursement patterns and to model the target pattern of expenditures.

100

101 Data and methods

102 Data for ESIF EC payments to MSs and regional authorities were obtained from the EC Directorate-General
103 for Regional and Urban Policy (DG REGIO). In every five-year financial programming period of the EU, each
104 individual MS systematically records the requests for payments (and related invoices) made by individual ben-
105 efiiciaries. However, these documents are neither standardised, or necessarily accessible, nor contain the same
106 information or structure across regions or MSs. Furthermore, the number of primary sources amounts to more
107 than 300 because the individual NMAs store their own records, which has made unsuccessful the attempts to
108 build these data bottom up due to the unreliable and incomplete information across MSs.
109 The current case study is grounded on the “official” database at the EC level. This dataset consists of around
110 500,000 entries, which include the yearly payments to the Operational Programmes (OPs) over four overarching
111 funding schemes (Cohesion Fund (CF), European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), ERDF,
112 European Social Fund (ESF)) and five programming periods (1989-1993, 1994-1999, 2000-2006, 2007-2013,
113 2014-2020). OPs are the reference unit and have variable geographical scope: regional, multi-regional, national,
114 or across multiple MSs. The EC does not directly collect information disaggregated at the regional level.
115 The pre-processing stage of this study involved regionalising EC payments over the 280 regions in Nomenclature
116 of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS), known as NUTS 2. Over time, the number and borders of NUTS2
117 regions have changed to reflect countries joining or leaving the EU, as well as administrative readjustments
118 within individual MSs. For this reason, during pre-processing, we harmonised the nomenclature to the NUTS2
119 2010 version, where each code maps uniquely onto a specific region. The detailed regionalisation procedure
120 is described in Wishlade, Michie, Familiari, Schneiderwind, and Resch [13] (work-package 13) and Lo Piano,
121 Chifari, Vidoni, and Saltelli [14]. Every entry in this regionalised EC dataset of payments corresponds to an
122 amount reimbursed to a given regional authority over a specific year, funding scheme, and programming period.

123 For the funding scheme ERDF, non-regionalised figures were attributed on a pro-capita basis to individual
124 NUTS2 areas for those countries that had not broken down the information at the NUTS2 level. If the region's
125 level of development was specified, a pro-capita attribution was performed among the NUTS2 areas with the
126 same level of development.

127 In this contribution, we cover the funding scheme ERDF reimbursed over the programming period 2007-2013.
128 We tested the modelled expenditures against the actual incurred expenditures for a pioneer MS, Italy (IT), whose
129 data were provided by the Italian responsible authority for this programming period and funding scheme. These
130 data are available from <https://opencoesione.gov.it/en/> and also included uncertified expenditures (i.e., figures
131 that have not yet been accounted for in the consolidated EC payments database).

132 Sensitivity analysis [15–17] was used to explore how uncertainty in the input variables affected the output vari-
133 able. Our analysis was performed within a factor-prioritisation [18] and direction-of-change setting; that is, we
134 aimed to identify the key drivers that influenced the output variable and the impact associated with fixing these
135 drivers, respectively. One of the most widely adopted approaches to sensitivity analysis is the variance-based ap-
136 proach, wherein output uncertainty is measured in terms of the statistical moment variance, which is eventually
137 apportioned to the input parameters. Another class of sensitivity methods, the moment-independent sensitivity
138 measures, do not resort to a particular statistical moment. As we will see in the next section, our output Quan-
139 tity of Interest (QoI) is the distance between the cumulative distributions of the expenditures, which naturally
140 supports the selection of a moment-independent sensitivity measure. Several moment-independent measures
141 have been proposed in the literature (see Borgonovo [19], Plischke, Borgonovo, and Smith [20], and Pianosi
142 and Wagener [21]). We hereby adopt the δ moment-independent sensitivity measure [19, 20] to evaluate how
143 the modelling parameters influence uncertainty regarding the distance between the modelled and the reported
144 expenditures.

145

146 Use of *distance* measures to estimate expenditure patterns

147 Consider a generic region p whose expenditures can be reimbursed over k eligible years. Let us also introduce a
148 *dummy* region against which we can benchmark the reported reimbursement patterns. The dummy region has a
149 constant spending and reimbursement pattern; specifically, it spends a certain amount and is reimbursed for the
150 same amount each year until the last eligible year of the programming period. For instance, if reimbursements
151 can occur over 10 years, the dummy region is reimbursed 10% each year of the total budget it has been granted.
152 For the sake of comparability, reimbursements are normalised across regions. The normalised cumulative ex-
153 penses of the dummy region over k years can be expressed as per equation 1:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k d_i = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{k} = 1 \quad (1)$$

154 Analogously, one can define the regional reimbursement pattern for a generic region p as follows:

$$R_p = \sum_{i=1}^k r_{p_i} = 1 \quad (2)$$

155 One may also define an equivalent of the Wasserstein metric in probability theory as the distance μ_p between
 156 the cumulatives of these two curves [12] according to equation 3:

$$\mu_p = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{o=1}^i |r_{p_o} - d_o| \quad (3)$$

157 To assess the time specificity of the reimbursement trend rather than the simple divergence from the regular
 158 *dummy* pattern, it is possible to address the plain difference in line with the Kruglov distance [12]. This is
 159 denoted by μ_p^s and can be expressed as follows:

$$\mu_p^s = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{o=1}^i (r_{p_o} - d_o) \quad (4)$$

160 These measures are complementary: μ_p acknowledges the divergence from a constant spending pattern,
 161 although it does not allow to grasp its time specificity (i.e., early versus late reimbursement pattern); conversely,
 162 μ_p^s addresses this specificity, although it suffers from compensatory effects across years (e.g., a positive difference
 163 in the year i would be cancelled out by an equal negative difference in the year $i + 1$). This makes it impossible
 164 to evaluate the precise reimbursement pattern at a yearly granularity through μ_p^s .

165 Let us now analyse the extreme case in which all the EC payments are reimbursed in the last eligible year
 166 of the programming period. In this case, the maximum difference μ_p would be:

$$\mu_p^s = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{o=1}^i |r_{p_o} - d_o| = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \left| -\frac{i}{k} \right| = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} i = \frac{k-1}{2} \quad (5)$$

167 Analogously, the assessment can be repeated for a hypothetical region whose expenditures are entirely
 168 reimbursed in the first year.

$$\mu_p = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{o=1}^i |r_{p_o} - d_o| = \sum_{i=1}^k \left| 1 - \frac{i}{k} \right| = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k |k - i| = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} |l| = \frac{k-1}{2} \quad (6)$$

169 The figures shown in equation 5 and equation 6 define the maximum threshold for our measurement. The
 170 minimum value zero is attained for a hypothetical region whose reimbursement pattern is identical to the *dummy*
 171 *region*.

172 One can easily obtain the values for the μ_p^s measurement, which is equivalent to μ_p in the case of an early
 173 reimbursement pattern. The sign is the opposite in the case of extremely late reimbursement and amounts
 174 to $-\frac{k-1}{2}$. Overall, regions anticipating the dummy spending pattern have a positive sign, whereas the sign is
 175 negative for regions with a delayed reimbursement pattern.

176 The two measures are complementary: μ_p measures the regularity of the reimbursement pattern, which is
 177 a property that policymakers will benefit from considering when managing the spending of granted financial
 178 resources. μ_p^s points to the specificity of the regional reimbursement pattern over the course of the entire
 179 programming period (delayed vs. early).

180 We use μ_p^s to define an index of regional specificity Ir that, in turn, enables us to rank regions and propose
 181 regional spending patterns, as detailed in the following section.

182 Taxonomy of cases

183 Let us consider the cumulative annual history of expenditures invoiced from the ultimate beneficiaries to the
184 NMAs, MS_p . E_p is our modelled cumulative expenditure, namely the quantity with which we attempt to
185 reproduce the pattern of MS_p . As per equation 7, the sum of the yearly figures over the entire programming
186 period must be equal to assure consistency.

$$\sum_{i=1}^k r_{p_i} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-m} ms_{p_i} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-m} e_{p_i} \quad (7)$$

187 EC payments are spread over k years, while expenditures are not eligible after the $(k - m)^{th}$ year of the
188 programming period.

189 A general rule is that reimbursements always follow expenses, which can be used as a basis for modelling
190 the yearly expenditure patterns. A situation wherein cumulative modelled expenditures are smaller than the
191 expenditures of NMAs would be wrong and would require the correction of our model.

192 For instance, let us take the first year of the programming period. In this year, the relation between the yearly
193 figures must be:

$$r_{p_1} \leq e_{p_1} \quad (8)$$

194 Furthermore, ms_{p_1} anticipates r_{p_1} , and the relation between these two quantities must also hold.

$$r_{p_1} \leq ms_{p_1} \quad (9)$$

195 Finally, significant differences between ms_{p_1} and e_{p_1} would not be plausible. ms_{p_1} also accounts for invoices
196 sent by local authorities (e.g., municipalities). This condition ensures that the time lag with e_{p_1} is minimal and,
197 in particular, below the yearly granularity at which these figures have been produced. Therefore, the relation
198 between the two figures should be:

$$ms_{p_1} \approx e_{p_1} \quad (10)$$

199 We can also extend these relations to the l^{th} year, with $l \leq k - m$, as per the following:

$$\sum_{i=1}^l r_{p_i} \leq \sum_{i=1}^l ms_{p_i} \approx \sum_{i=1}^l e_{p_i} \quad (11)$$

200 Therefore, our workflow will firstly focus on evaluating the closure relation as per equation 8, although
201 uncertified expenditures may result in discrepancies of variable magnitude.

202 Modelling the incurred expenditures

203 In this contribution, we use an adaptation of the model to estimate local expenditures from the reported EC
204 payments [14, 22]. The model was developed based on joint reflections among practitioners in technical fields
205 such as modelling and data analysis, as well as practitioners involved in the operation of EU regional policy

206 programmes. The rationale of the model is to project the reimbursed payments backwards to capture the actual
 207 temporality of the reimbursed financial resources, along with their effects on the local receiving areas.

208 An overarching assumption of the model is that each yearly expenditure corresponds only to a fraction of the
 209 payment reimbursed in the same year. The complementary fraction of this payment is attributed to expenditures
 210 incurred over the previous year(s).

211 Yearly expenditures are estimated by ranking each EU region against a dummy region, as discussed in the
 212 previous subsections. In turn, a coefficient of regional specificity Ir_p is calculated from the ranks of μ^s over
 213 each individual funding scheme and programming period. This coefficient is used to define the spending pattern
 214 of regions. The higher its value, the greater is the delay that characterises the region's reimbursement pattern
 215 compared to the dummy region's constant reimbursement pattern.

216 Feature scaling, also known as min-max normalisation, was performed on the Ir_p series. This leads to a value
 217 of 0 for the region with the earliest reimbursement pattern and 1 for the latest.

218 For instance, consider $Ir_p = 0.6$ for the ERDF funding scheme over the 2007-2013 programming period. This
 219 implies that the payment reported in the last eligible year of expenditures is attributed to expenditures that
 220 were also incurred over a maximum of $\text{int}((2017 - 2007) * Ir_p^{2007-2013,ERDF}) = 6$ previous years.

221 The uncertain parameters in the model, as shown in Table 1, are:

- 222 • Maximum share of payment attributed to an expenditure incurred on the same year ϕ_{max}
- 223 • Minimum share of payment attributed to an expenditure incurred on the same year ϕ_{min}
- 224 • Number of *Years* of expenditures that the residual payment can be attributed to backwards, which is
 225 defined as $\text{int}((k-1) * Ir_p^{pp,fs})$ for a generic region p over the programming period pp and the funding scheme
 226 fs

227 The other uncertain parameter is a binary trigger related to non-attributed NMAs expenditures. These are
 228 expenditures that do not map onto specific NUTS2 areas. This regional reattribution is proportional either
 229 to the funds reimbursed on the year of the unattributed payment or to the funds reimbursed over the whole
 230 programming period. Table 1 specifies the uncertainty range of these input parameters.

231 The range of the distributions of the input parameters was selected after consultation with practitioners directly
 232 involved in EU regional policy programmes. For continuous variables, uniform distributions were conservatively
 233 adopted due to the absence of information concerning the individual probability of values across the range.

Table 1: Summary of parameters and their distribution. \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{U} indicate discrete and uniform, respectively.

Parameter	Description	Distribution
ϕ_{max}	Maximum share	$\mathcal{U}(0.8, 1)$
ϕ_{min}	Minimum share	$\mathcal{U}(0.2, 0.4)$
<i>Residual selector</i>	Binary trigger for non-clear NUTS 2 expenditure IT database	$\mathcal{D}(0, 1)$
<i>Years</i>	Number of previous years from the last year of eligible expenditures	$\mathcal{D}(1, \text{integer}((k-1) * Ir_p^{pp,fs}))$

234 The share of the payment attributed to an expenditure occurring in the same year is denoted by ϕ_p , which
235 is expressed as follows:

$$\phi_p = \phi_{max,p} - Ir_p^{pp,fs} * (\phi_{max,p} - \phi_{min,p}) \quad (12)$$

236 The quantity ϕ_p is constant across years. Also, the resulting expenditure incurred over year i is equal to:

$$e_{pi} = r_{pi} * \phi_p \quad (13)$$

237 The greater the value of $Ir_p^{pp,fs}$, the lower the share of the payments attributed to expenditures incurred on
238 that specific year. The rationale for this hypothesis is that a later reimbursement pattern most likely results
239 from conspicuous time lags between the incurred expenditures and the reimbursed payments.

240 The residual of the payment (i.e., the fraction of the payment not attributed to expenditures incurred in the
241 same year) is spread onto the previous years as per the third uncertain parameter, *Years*. To demonstrate,
242 consider the task of attributing the residual of the 2017 payment over the three previous years. In this case, a
243 fraction of the payment reimbursed in the year 2017 is attributed to expenditures incurred in the years 2016,
244 2015, and 2014 under the assumption that these are halving each preceding year: specifically, $\frac{4}{7}$ of the residual
245 of the 2017 payment is attributed to expenditures incurred in 2016, $\frac{2}{7}$ in 2015, and $\frac{1}{7}$ in 2014. The rationale
246 behind this assumption is that the magnitude of a payment is most likely more strongly correlated with more
247 recent expenditures.

248 The assumption is also made that the total number of backward years of expenditures that the residual of the
249 payment is attributed to is correlated over the programming period; in particular, we assume that it decreases
250 by one year each preceding year. In this way, if the residual of the 2017 payment is attributed to expenditures
251 incurred over the three previous years, this quantity would only amount to two for the residual of the payment
252 reimbursed in the year 2016, and one for 2015. The minimum number of backward years is one, and this
253 quantity is kept constant for all the years backwards up to the second year of the programming period once this
254 threshold is met. Payments reimbursed in the first year of the programming period are entirely attributed to
255 expenditures incurred in the same year.

256 In total, 2^{17} ($\sim 130,000$) Monte Carlo simulations were performed by sampling the uncertainty parameters from
257 these distributions through quasi-random LP_τ Sobol' low-discrepancy sequences [23]. This sample size was se-
258 lected to ensure the convergence of the sensitivity indices (see the convergence plots in [Supporting Material](#)).
259 The rationale for using Monte Carlo simulations was to generate a population of expenditure distributions and
260 to evaluate their reliability against figures reported by the NMAs. The Python scripts are available as Jupyter
261 Notebooks on [GitHub](#).

262 The Python scripts thoroughly describe the preparation and curation of the dataset for the comparison, as well
263 as the uncertainty analysis performed. The output variable is the cumulative distance μ^s between the reported
264 IT expenditure and the modelled expenditure previously introduced. After consulting with practitioners in-
265 volved in EU regional policy programmes, the assumption was made that the last year of eligible expenditures

266 was 2017.

267 To understand how the uncertainty of the input parameters reflected onto the output uncertainty moment-
268 independent sensitivity analysis was performed using a *Matlab*[®] *Betaks3* subroutine. In moment-independent
269 sensitivity analysis, the sensitivity measure is the distance between the unconditional and conditional distribu-
270 tions of the uncertain parameters. The δ sensitivity measure [19, 20] is calculated for the four input parameters
271 shown in Table 1. The logic behind δ is the following: one factor is fixed to a value, and the difference between
272 the curve obtained by fixing this factor and the standard output curve is measured. If the factor is important,
273 fixing it will tangibly affect the output in terms of curve shape. The experiment is repeated by fixing the factor
274 at different values over its range of variability until an average difference is obtained.

275 Results and discussion

276 The distance against the reported MS expenditures for the modelled expenditures and payments for Italy (IT)
277 is illustrated in Fig. 1. Mismatches between the certified and uncertified data amount to approximately 10% of
278 the former.

279

Fig. 1: Boxplots of distributions of yearly cumulative distance between modelled and reported expenditures. Black rectangles show the range of yearly cumulative distance between the reported EC payments and reported expenditures to Italian NMAs.

280 In Fig. 1, the boxplots are always below the threshold range defined by the distance with the reported EC
281 payments (black rectangles), with no or a (mostly) minor degree of superimposition. This indicates that the
282 model is moving the estimated expenditures in the right direction. The regions with the widest distributions
283 are Lazio (Laz), Calabria (Clb), Sicily (Scl), and Sardinia (Srd). Conversely, Aosta Valley (AsV) and Trentino-

Fig. 2: Distributions for (a) Mls, Cmp, FVG, and Laz; and (b) Lmb, Apl, EmR, and Tsc Number of occurrences in the simulation against cumulative distance between estimated and reported expenditures.

284 South Tyrol (TST) are the regions with the narrowest distributions.
 285 By examining the shapes of the distributions, it is possible to identify multi-peak and/or multi-modal distribu-
 286 tions for certain regions. The most emblematic cases are Molise (Mls), Campania (Cmp), Friuli Venezia Giulia
 287 (FVG), and Laz, as shown in Fig. 2a. By contrast, Lombardy (Lmb), Apulia (Apl), Emilia-Romagna (EmR),
 288 and Tuscany (Tsc) show the most normal distributions, but they still exhibit some degree of skewness (Fig. 2b).

289 The remaining cases are provided in [Supporting Material](#). By examining the regional Ir_p , it is not possible
 290 to identify a precise correlation between this value and the distribution's width, skewness, or level of multi-
 291 modality.

292 Uncertainty analysis enables the investigator to apportion the output uncertainty onto the input parameters.
 293 The use of moment-independent sensitivity analysis is *a fortiori* justified by the skewed and multi-modal distri-
 294 butions obtained, which implies that variance is a potentially poor measure of output uncertainty in these
 295 settings. The values of the sensitivity measure δ are reported in Figure 3. The higher the value, the more
 296 influential the uncertainty of the input parameter on the output uncertainty.

297
 298 The variable *Residual selector* was identified as the most influential parameter for 10 of 20 Italian regions,
 299 *Years* for 8, and ϕ_{max} for the remainder. Figures 4 and 5 show an example for each of the two first cases,
 300 respectively. The charts for the other regions can be found in [Supporting Material](#). In Figure 4, one can
 301 appreciate how the different values of the trigger *Residual selector* 'activate' each part of the bi-modal-shaped
 302 distribution. The trend is similar in Figure 5, where the distinct sub-components of the output distribution are
 303 activated by different values of *Years* (Figure 5). In the *y given ϕ_{min} sub-Figure*, one can also appreciate the
 304 importance of this parameter, given the wide range explored in the output shape upon varying this continuous
 305 parameter in its range.

306 This information can be used to inform a factor-prioritisation strategy [15] focused at reducing the QoI
 307 (i.e., the cumulative distance with the reported MS expenditures) by fixing the most influential parameters to
 308 the value that would minimise this quantity. At this point, let us assume that it is possible to choose either

Fig. 3: Moment-independent sensitivity measure δ for uncertain parameters in the pool of Italian regions and the average figure across regions.

309 one option or the other for the trigger *Residual selector*. On doing so, the option of attributing the residual
 310 according to the reported regional yearly expenditures will lead to a lower distance in the case of FVG (Fig-
 311 ure 6a). This trend is shared by 16 of the 20 Italian regions, as shown in [Supporting Material](#). The trajectory
 312 is similar if the other parameter with the greatest influence, *Years*, is fixed towards its higher end, as indicated
 313 in the example of Clb in Figure 6b. This trend is shared by 18 of the 20 Italian regions (see [Supporting Material](#)).

314

315 When fixing both these parameters at their optimal values, one obtains a reduction for 18 of the 20 regions.
 316 Notably, however, Laz is one of the two regions showing an opposite trend ([Supporting Material](#)).

317 These findings are encouraging, yet the sample of regions investigated is too small to conclude that fixing these
 318 factors is an effective strategy to reduce the output variability and simplify the model developed: figures for
 319 more MSs would be needed to draw robust inferences that corroborates potential adjustments.

320 Existing interactions among the parameters justifies the choice of global sensitivity analysis over a plain one-
 321 variable-at-a-time approach, that would overlook them. Using variance-based sensitivity analysis [15], where the
 322 sensitivity metric is the variance of the output cumulative distance, more than 10% of the output variance would
 323 not be attributed for two regions: Liguria (Lgr) and Cmp. Only 80% of the output variance is apportioned when
 324 neglecting interactions among factors for the latter, while this is only 55% for the former, for which interactions

Fig. 4: Conditional output distributions for Laz when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

among factors are responsible for 45% of the output variance.

Conclusions

This study presented a model to infer incurred expenditures for European regions from the reported reimbursement pattern of EC funds. The data-driven model elaborated more reliable local time-resolved figures based on the patterns reported in official centralised figures. In our study, we also validated the output time-resolved database through benchmarking against the local official statistics. We showcased an application of our model for the ERDF by considering the example of Italy for the programming period 2007-2013.

The work presented here aligns closely with several of the core principles of the European Statistics Code of Practice. In particular, it is consistent with Principle 4, Commitment to Quality, because it develops procedures to monitor and improve the quality of the statistical data processes, also favouring the integration of data from multiple sources. It is also aligned with Principle 12, Accuracy and Reliability, through its assessment and validation of source data, integrated data, intermediate results, and statistical outputs.

The model implemented in this study can move from EC payments to simulated expenditures in a way that matches the actual expenditures on the ground as closely as possible. Testing involved comparing the cumulative trends of the modelled and reported expenditures for the Italian regions. Perfect closure against this benchmark was not possible due to around 10% uncertified expenditures. Reducing this gap would enable analysts to

Fig. 5: Conditional output distributions for Clb when fixing the uncertain input parameters.

Fig. 6: Conditional distributions of distance against the initial distribution of (a) FVG on *Residual selector*; and b) Clb on *Years*.

341 assess the quality of the modelling activity performed more effectively. This modelling exercise would need to
 342 be extended across EU regions to backstop its findings, although it will never be perfect due to the existence of
 343 multiple intervening factors (e.g., payment suspensions, issues with the management of individual OPs or with
 344 the processing of the data at any level, and strategic decisions for reporting expenditures). Nonetheless, the
 345 figures produced in this study at the individual NUTS2 level for IT proved to be quite reliable.
 346 Uncertainty and sensitivity analyses enabled this study's assessment of the range of uncertainty in the temporal
 347 discrepancies between the reported and modelled expenditures, as well as its apportionment onto the input

348 parameters and assumptions, respectively. The most impactful assumptions turned out to be the following:
349 first, how the non-clearly regionalised expenditures are spread onto individual regions, *Residual selector*; and
350 second, the number of backward years onto which the residual of the yearly payments is spread, *Years*. We
351 re-ran our simulation by keeping these variables fixed at precise points in the admissible range. The results of
352 the sensitivity analysis for the two parameters show that both increasing the number of years of backward shift
353 and attributing the non-clearly regionalised expenditures (on the basis of yearly regional expenditures) may
354 improve the match between the modelled and measures expenditures. However, the gain was marginal for some
355 regions and the fit was worse for 2 regions out of 20.

356 These findings are encouraging given the simplicity of the model developed. Further sophistication may be
357 adopted to better reproduce the MS expenditures reported, as well as to corroborate this factor-prioritisation
358 strategy.

359 The following are the principal take-home messages for different stakeholders:

- 360 • The EC may expand this research to other funding schemes and programming periods, including the
361 current recovery funds for member states.
- 362 • Further MSs can make their figures available to strengthen the findings presented here. Standardised tools
363 and forms for registering all payments would be helpful, along with data access for the researcher, ideally
364 through central storage at the DG REGIO.
- 365 • The model's validation against MSs figures provides a new database that econometricians can use to
366 generate less time-lagged and more reliable estimates of the benefits of European funds on the ground.
- 367 • The community of official statisticians may seek to replicate this case study in other relevant examples,
368 including other funding schemes, international aid funds, and trade figures.

369 **Supporting Material**

370 The script used to perform the computations in this research is available from [the project GitHub repository](#).

371 The additional charts referred to in this document are accessible from [Supporting Material](#).

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375 **Declaration of competing interests**

376 The authors report no potential competing interests.

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